

Experimental

Healthy, mature and ripe olive fruits were collected from its growing area at Bhadrawah in Jammu region at an altitude of about 1000 m above the mean sea level to study their physicochemical characteristics. The average weight, size, and mesocarp and kernel ratio of the fruits were observed. Moisture, ash, oil and protein content in the fruits were assayed by AOAC methods⁹. The oil was extracted from the mesocarp of the fruits by petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) and purified⁴ for studying the fatty acid composition. The methyl esters of fatty acids were analysed through glc following the procedure of Kates⁵. A Pye–Unicam glc instrument equipped with hydrogen flame ionisation detector was used having glass column (200 cm × 0.6 cm) packed with 15% Reoplex on 80/100 mesh Chromosorb-W. Nitrogen was used as carrier gas with a flow rate of 35 ml min⁻¹. The column was operated isothermally at 190°; the injection port and detector temperatures being 270° and 300°, respectively.

Results and Discussion

The mesocarp of ripe olive fruits contained total ash, 2.1–2.4%; oil, 12.1–19.4%; crude protein, 2.5–2.8%; and moisture, 46.5–60.3%. On dry-weight basis, the oil constitutes 30–36% of the mesocarp. Fruits of 'Ascolina' are larger in size and weight (6.6 g/fruit) and having higher moisture content (60.3%) in comparison to 'Ascotrinia' having smaller size and lower weight (2.9 g/fruit) and moisture (46.5%) contents (Table 1). Iodine values of oil of both the varieties are lower than the values reported^{6–8}. The oil contained 0.9% unsaponifiable matter and 1.1–1.3% free fatty acids. These characteristics of lower iodine value and unsaponifiable

matter are within the acceptable limits of edibility^{9–10}.

Oleic acid constitutes 65.0 and 73.4% of the oil in Ascotrinia and Ascolina varieties, respectively (Table 1). In addition to oleic acid, palmitic and linoleic acids are the other constituents of the oil which constitute 24.5 and 16.0%, and 10.0 and 10.5% in Ascotrinia and Ascolina, respectively. A 0.5% eicosenoic acid was also found in Ascotrinia fruit oil (Table 1). The olives grown in Jammu region have marked similarity to those grown in Himachal Pradesh¹¹.

The characteristics of olive fruits and their oils obtained from Jammu region are similar to that of the European varieties. Moreover, the oil having lower iodine value and free fatty acids shows its greater dietary acceptance.

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TABLE 1—CHARACTERISTICS AND FATTY ACID COMPOSITION* OF OLIVE FRUIT OIL

Parameters	Ascotrinia	Ascolina
(a) Fruit		
Weight of fruit (g)	2.9	6.6
Kernel (%)	20	16
Pulp (%)	80	84
Moisture (%)	46.5	60.3
Ash (%)	2.1	2.4
Protein (%)	2.6	2.8
Oil (%)	19.4	12.1
Oil (dry wt. basis) (%)	36	30
(b) Fruit oil		
Iodine value	68	69
Saponification value	199	197
Unsaponifiable matter (%)	0.9	0.9
Free fatty acids (%)	1.1	1.3
Fatty acids :		
C16:0	24.5	16.0
C18:0	—	trace
C18:1	65.0	73.4
C18:2	10.0	10.5
C18:3	traces	—
C20:1	0.5	—

*Values are means of triplicate determinations.

AAS Determination of Zinc after Separation with Liquid Chelating Exchanger and its Application to the Ganga River Water

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FLAME and flameless atomic absorption spectrophotometric (AAS) determination of zinc has been described by several authors^{1–5}. In most of the cases, different chelating agents have been used

followed by extraction in suitable solvents. Solvent extraction behaviour of zinc with liquid ion-exchangers has also been studied^{6,7}. The present communication reports the determination of zinc by AAS after its extraction with a new β -diketo liquid chelating exchanger⁸ ($\text{RCOCH}_2\text{COCH}_3$) in chloroform as diluent. The effects of different variables have been investigated. The method has been applied successfully in the determination of zinc in the Ganga river water.

Experimental

β -Diketo liquid chelating exchanger: Versatic-10 (C_{10} -isomeric monocarboxylic acid, Shell Chemical, London) was purified by distilling at $\sim 244^\circ$ and the exchanger was prepared in two steps⁹. Versatic-10 was mixed with a large excess of absolute ethanol and a little concentrated H_2SO_4 , and refluxed for 24 h. The resulting ethyl ester was separated and purified by distillation. The ester was then condensed with large excess of pure acetone in presence of sodium ethoxide by refluxing the mixture for 24 h and the resulting liquid β -diketo compound was separated and purified.

The physical characteristics of the chelating exchanger were found to be as follows: mol. wt., 212; density, 0.9064 g cm^{-3} at 30° ; ν_{max} $1705 - 1710 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ corresponding to diketo group; $\tau - 1.6$ indicating the presence of an enolic OH due to intramolecular hydrogen bonding.

Standard zinc(II) solution: A solution of zinc was prepared by dissolving $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (E. Merck) in double-distilled water and was standardised by complexometric titration. The solution was diluted to a zinc concentration of 9.9 ppm.

Diverse ions: Stock solution were prepared from pure sample of the nitrates, chlorides and sulphates of various metals or other convenient salts.

All other chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade.

Apparatus: A Shimadzu 646 atomic absorption spectrophotometer was used with the following conditions: zinc hollow cathode lamp current, 6 mA; burner height, 4 mm; wavelength, 213.9 nm; slit-width, 3.8 Å; air-flow rate, 10 l/m; acetylene-flow rate, 2.4 l/m; optimum concentration range, 0.4–1.6 ppm Zn. The pH values were measured with a Sambros 335 digital pH meter.

General procedure: The general extraction procedure is based upon solvent extraction technique. To an aqueous solution (1 ml) containing 9.9 μg zinc, was added dilute ammonium hydroxide solution and the pH adjusted to 8.0. After adding tris-buffer (2 ml), total volume of the aqueous phase was made up to 10 ml with distilled water and taken in a 50 ml separatory funnel. A 0.1 M solution (2 ml) of chelating exchanger in chloroform was then added and shaken for 1 min and allowed to settle for 2 min. The organic phase was

then separated carefully to another separatory funnel. To remove any trace of organic solvent entrained in the separated aqueous phase, the latter was washed with chloroform ($2 \times 5 \text{ ml}$). The resulting chloroform extract was mixed in the same separatory funnel containing the separated organic phase, and was stripped with 0.1 N HCl (5 ml). The aqueous phase was collected in a 10 ml volumetric flask and made up to the mark with distilled water. The absorbance value of the resulting solution was measured on the AAS in air– C_2H_2 flame at 213.9 nm against a reagent blank. The amount of zinc was computed from the calibration curve.

Application to natural water: The estimation of zinc was made in the Ganga river water near Tribeni–Kuntighat industrial area in the district of Hooghly. The sample preparation, storage and preliminary treatment was the same as described earlier¹⁰. After reducing the volume of water samples by evaporation, zinc was extracted and separated by applying the liquid chelating exchanger under the experimental condition. Then stripping the organic phase with 0.1 N HCl, the aqueous phase was aspirated into AAS.

Results and Discussion

Optimisation of different parameters: The amount of extraction of zinc with the liquid chelating exchanger at different pH has been studied and the working pH range for the quantitative extraction is 6.8–9.2. The extraction behaviour of zinc indicates that quantitative extraction (100%) of the metal occurs with chloroform, benzene and xylene. Extraction with other diluents shows 97.4% in carbon tetrachloride, 92.1% in methyl isobutyl ketone and nitrobenzene, and 83.4% in cyclohexane. The effect of extractant concentration was studied by varying the concentration of a fixed volume of the chelating exchanger from 0.075 to 0.600 M in chloroform. It was found that the extraction was complete at 0.200 M chelating exchanger. For the complete stripping of zinc from chloroform layer, HCl solutions of various strengths (0.05–3.0 N) were used. In all cases the stripping was quantitative and 0.1 N HCl was used. The period of shaking for extraction as well as stripping time was varied from 5 min to 15 s. It was observed that 30 s was enough for quantitative extraction and back-stripping was complete within 15 s.

Effect of foreign ions: The effect of various ions on the quantitative extraction of zinc were studied under the experimental condition. For 9.9 ppm zinc, tolerance limits (within an error of $\pm 2\%$) for diverse ions have been found to be as follows: Ca^{II} , Ba^{II} , Mo^{VI} , W^{VI} (300 ppm each); Sr^{II} , Mg^{II} (350 ppm each); Sn^{II} (52 ppm); Cr^{VI} (500 ppm); Ti^{IV} (400 ppm); Cu^{II} , Al^{III} , Fe^{III} (12 ppm each); Ni^{II} , Mn^{II} , Co^{II} , Pb^{II} (100 ppm each). The interference due to Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} can be avoided by using I^- as a masking agent. In order to develop a possible analytical application

NOTES

for extraction of zinc, several synthetic mixtures were studied (Table 1).

TABLE 1—RECOVERY OF ZINC IN SYNTHETIC MIXTURES

Sl. no.	Composition	Recovery of Zn %
1.	Zn ^{II} (9.9)+Ni ^{II} (100)+Co ^{II} (100)	101
2.	Zn ^{II} (9.9)+Ba ^{II} (300)+Al ^{III} (12)	100
3.	Zn ^{II} (9.9)+Mo ^{VI} (300)+Sn ^{II} (52)	99
4.	Zn ^{II} (9.9)+Ti ^{IV} (400)+Cr ^{VI} (500)	100
5.	Zn ^{II} (9.9)+Ca ^{II} (300)+Cr ^{VI} (500)+Mo ^{VI} (300)	100
6.	Zn ^{II} (9.9)+Fe ^{III} (12)+Cu ^{II} (12)+Ni ^{II} (100)	101
7.	Zn ^{II} (9.9)+Pb ^{II} (100)+Mn ^{II} (100)+Ni ^{II} (100)	98
8.	Zn ^{II} (9.9)+Mn ^{II} (100)+W ^{VI} (300)+Mg ^{II} (350)	99

Nature of extracted species: In order to determine the composition of the extracted species, the extractions were carried out keeping the zinc ion concentration constant and varying pH of the medium. From the equation¹¹,

$$\log D = \log K_{ex} + (m+n) \log [H(LCE)] + n \text{ pH}$$

(where, *D* is distribution ratio, *K_{ex}* the extraction constant, *m* the number of adduct molecule, *n* the number of chelating agent bound to the metal and *H(LCE)* the chelating agent), it is evident that the plot of log *D* vs pH will give a slope *n* which indicates the number of H⁺ ion liberated from the ligand during complexation with the metal ion, and it gives a straight line with a slope value of 1.8. So it can be concluded that two H⁺ ions have been liberated during complexation with zinc(II). Hence the extractable complex may be considered to be bis-chelated. Again the plot of log *D* vs log [LCE] at pH 8.0 and at fixed [Zn⁺] gives a straight line with a slope value of 2.3 which conforms the bis-chelated nature of the complex. On the other hand, plotting (log *D* - 2 pH) vs log [LCE] a straight line has been obtained with a slope value of 1.9 indicating (*m+n*)=2, i.e. *m*=0. Hence no adduct with the extracting species is formed and the stoichiometry of the extracted complex is Zn(LCE)₂. Thus the extraction equilibria of zinc may be represented as

where, o and a are respectively organic and aqueous phase.

Application: The proposed method has been applied to the determination of zinc in the Ganga river water at six different stations. The results

are shown in Table 2. As the results indicate that the samples give lower zinc content by direct AAS, it is always suggested to extract the pre-concentrated

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF ZINC IN NATURAL WATER

Sl. no.	Sampling station	Zn content (μg dm ⁻³)	
		By direct AAS	By AAS after separation
1.	Tribenighat	55	118
2.	Tribeni Tissue	275	310
3.	Lakshmitalaghat	50	150
4.	Bandel Thermal Plant (near chimney)	20	35
5.	Kesoram Rayon	48	60
6.	Bandel Thermal Plant (near office)	4	40

river water samples with the chelating exchanger and then run AAS. Nevertheless, the results show a variation of 35 to 310 μg Zn/dm³ water at various stations. The highest zinc content in Tribeni Tissue station (Sl. no. 2) is alarming (allowed excessive limit 0.01 ppm¹²) to the people specially who are consuming this water. The efficiency of the method in releasing zinc from water was determined by adding known amounts of zinc to the untreated Ganga river water samples followed by pre-concentration and determination of Zn in recoveries by the proposed method (Table 3).

TABLE 3—RECOVERY OF ZINC FROM NATURAL WATER

Amount of zinc (μg dm ⁻³)		Recovery of Zn %
Added	Found	
0	60.0	—
50.0	112.0	101.8
100.0	159.6	99.7
150.0	213.2	101.5
200.0	263.1	101.1
250.0	307.4	99.1

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